

Ion Exchange Equilibrium Studies in Niobium Arsenate

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The synthesis, ion exchange properties and analytical potentiality of niobium arsenate were investigated earlier. The present paper deals with the alkali and alkaline earth metal ion equilibrium studies at 30, 50 and 70°. Some values for K_H^M , ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔS_{zx}° have been calculated.

STUDIES on insoluble acid salts of polybasic metals which act as cation exchangers are continuously increasing owing to their excellent stability towards radiations and high temperature. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate the ion exchange behaviour of these materials through thermodynamic equilibrium experiments at different temperatures.

In course of our systematic investigations of ion exchange materials based on niobium, synthesis, characterisation, ion exchange properties and analytical potentiality of niobium arsenate^{1,2}, niobium antimonate^{3,4} and niobium molybdate⁵ have been published. But almost all these studies were lacking in thermodynamic aspects of the exchange equilibrium. A number of such equilibrium studies⁶⁻¹⁴ have been reported on zeolites and on different phases of zirconium phosphate but not on niobium based ion exchange materials. The present report summarizes the thermodynamic behaviour for $\text{Na}^+ \rightarrow \text{H}^+$, $\text{K}^+ \rightarrow \text{H}^+$, $\text{Mg}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{H}^+$, $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{H}^+$, $\text{Sr}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{H}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{H}^+$ exchange equilibria on niobium arsenate at 30, 50 and 70°.

Materials and Method: Niobium pentoxide (B.D.H., England), sodium arsenate (Riedel, Germany) and other reagents of analytical grade were used. Niobium pentoxide was dissolved in sulphuric acid containing ammonium sulphate as reported earlier¹. Niobium arsenate (Nb/As=1.79) was prepared by mixing 0.1M niobium sulphate and 0.1M sodium arsenate solutions in the volume ratio 1:4 at pH ~1. The resultant material was sieved to obtain 50-100 mesh size particles. It was converted into hydrogen form by placing the material in 2-3M HNO₃. The H⁺ form of the exchanger was then converted to the metal ion form by placing in 0.1M solutions of respective metal chlorides for 24 hrs with intermittent replacement of the solution. All samples were washed till free from chloride ions and dried at 40° in an incubator.

The water content of different metallic forms of niobium arsenate was measured by heating at 220°

for 2 hrs. The ion exchange capacity was determined by elution with 1M alkali nitrate and 0.5M alkaline earth chloride solutions. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—WATER CONTENT AND ION EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF NIOBIUM ARSENATE TOWARDS VARIOUS CATIONS

Cationic form	Eluent	Water content (%)	I. E. C. for H ⁺ exchange (meq/g)	Hydrated radius (Å)
H ⁺	—	9.28	—	—
Na ⁺	1M NaNO ₃	6.92	0.90	2.76
K ⁺	1M KNO ₃	7.56	0.98	2.32
Mg ²⁺	0.5M MgCl ₂	10.40	0.80	7.00
Ca ²⁺	0.5M CaCl ₂	11.80	0.86	6.30
Sr ²⁺	0.5M SrCl ₂	14.20	0.86	—
Ba ²⁺	0.5M BaCl ₂	14.40	0.94	5.90

In the equilibrium experiments 0.5 g niobium arsenate in the H⁺ form was shaken with 50 ml of a solution containing nitric acid and the metal nitrate. The ionic strengths were 0.20M and 0.1M with respect to alkali metal ions and alkaline earth metal ions respectively. The system was shaken for 8 hrs. Equilibrium was attained within 8 hrs at all temperatures. The determination of Na and K was carried out by AIMIL Flame Photometer. Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba were determined by titration against standard EDTA using Eriochrome Black-T as an indicator. The results of equilibrium experiments at 30° only are given in Tables 2-7.

The reversibility experiments were performed by equilibrating the respective metal forms of the exchanger with nitric acid and metal ion solutions for 8 hrs.

Results and Discussion

The ion exchange capacity and water content values for Na, K, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba forms of niobium arsenate are given in Table 1. The water content in all the six forms increases with the

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TABLE 2—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR Na⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE IN NIOBIUM ARSENATE AT 30±2°

X _{Na}	X̄ _{Na}	S _H ^{Na}	f _H	f̄ _{Na}	K _H ^{Na}	Av.K _H ^{Na}
0.082	0.002	0.0693	—	—	—	
0.054	0.065	1.2180	0.98	1.03	1.236	
0.075	0.112	1.5550	0.96	0.78	1.216	
0.110	0.130	1.2090	0.99	1.01	1.210	
0.158	0.215	1.4590	0.97	0.86	—	1.205
0.281	0.255	1.4000	0.98	1.02	1.203	
0.297	0.335	1.1650	0.97	1.12	—	
0.360	0.390	1.1370	0.94	0.96	1.168	
0.518	0.490	1.1140	—	—	—	
0.699	0.609	0.7038	0.63	1.03	1.196	

TABLE 6—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR Sr²⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE AT 30±2°

X _{Sr}	X̄ _{Sr}	S _H ^{Sr}	f _H	f̄ _{Sr}	K _H ^{Sr}	Av.K _H ^{Sr}
0.250	0.081	0.2397	0.95	1.20	0.3981	
0.378	0.126	0.1781	0.94	1.35	—	
0.436	0.158	0.1388	0.88	2.06	0.3684	
0.525	0.184	0.1347	0.86	2.10	0.3824	
0.562	0.212	0.1308	0.88	2.30	0.3887	
0.600	0.224	0.1128	0.80	2.20	0.3877	0.3868
0.628	0.250	0.1268	0.83	2.10	0.3770	
0.646	0.269	0.1283	0.74	1.60	0.3750	
0.666	0.293	0.1307	0.80	2.10	—	
0.694	0.293	0.1119	0.74	2.05	0.4165	

TABLE 3—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR K⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE AT 30±2°

X _K	X̄ _K	S _H ^K	f _H	f̄ _K	K _H ^K	Av.K _H ^K
0.034	0.040	1.1570	0.99	0.52	0.6148	
0.080	0.050	0.6052	0.95	0.67	—	
0.117	0.075	0.6120	0.95	0.82	0.5508	
0.163	0.082	0.4586	0.94	1.08	0.5249	
0.250	0.110	0.3708	0.94	1.49	0.5872	0.5702
0.332	0.150	0.2483	0.89	1.93	0.5562	
0.425	0.162	0.2616	0.83	1.81	0.5705	
0.516	0.180	0.2059	0.81	2.20	0.5734	
0.652	0.350	0.2875	0.81	1.72	0.5856	

TABLE 7—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR Ba²⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE AT 30±2°

X _{Ba}	X̄ _{Ba}	S _H ^{Ba}	f _H	f̄ _{Ba}	K _H ^{Ba}	Av.K _H ^{Ba}
0.091	0.056	0.7441	0.97	0.75	0.5974	
0.205	0.089	0.3705	0.95	1.266	0.5142	
0.340	0.109	0.1991	0.84	2.14	0.6027	
0.392	0.135	0.1994	0.87	2.26	0.5793	
0.438	0.151	0.1826	0.83	2.45	0.6339	
0.453	0.176	0.2121	0.83	2.36	—	0.6042
0.555	0.179	0.0957	0.81	4.20	0.6182	
0.592	0.211	0.1108	0.74	2.86	0.6223	
0.623	0.240	0.1275	0.78	3.19	0.6676	
0.654	0.264	0.1237	0.72	3.20	—	
0.678	0.288	0.1142	0.66	2.31	0.6026	

TABLE 4—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR Mg²⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE AT 30±2°

X _{Mg}	X̄ _{Mg}	S _H ^{Mg}	f _H	f̄ _{Mg}	K _H ^{Mg}	Av.K _H ^{Mg}
0.169	0.047	0.021	0.70	5.12	0.2193	
0.286	0.074	0.169	1.0002	1.12	—	
0.426	0.080	0.0825	0.84	2.00	0.2337	
0.503	0.100	0.0492	0.82	3.40	0.2393	
0.579	0.111	0.0524	0.82	3.43	0.2673	0.2513
0.633	0.127	0.0489	0.75	2.23	—	
0.672	0.137	0.0391	0.68	3.34	0.2480	
0.686	0.156	0.0423	0.70	3.05	0.2538	
0.683	0.194	0.0574	0.76	3.00	0.2979	
0.721	0.194	0.0044	0.48	6.98	—	

TABLE 5—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT, SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR Ca²⁺→H⁺ EXCHANGE AT 30±2°

X _{Ca}	X̄ _{Ca}	S _H ^{Ca}	f _H	f̄ _{Ca}	K _H ^{Ca}	Av.K _H ^{Ca}
0.286	0.075	0.1625	0.92	1.02	0.2465	
0.428	0.110	0.1093	0.70	1.50	—	
0.537	0.126	0.0730	0.70	1.84	0.2743	
0.633	0.126	0.0367	0.66	2.89	0.2439	
0.638	0.155	0.0407	0.65	2.82	0.2719	0.2685
0.656	0.184	0.0505	0.64	2.30	0.2902	
0.686	0.195	0.0424	0.68	2.90	0.2658	
0.688	0.232	0.0593	0.64	2.20	—	
0.714	0.232	0.0471	0.59	2.10	0.2841	
0.724	0.250	0.0403	0.52	1.82	0.2711	

decrease in the hydrated radii of the ions. This indicates that the metal ions enter into the matrix in their hydrated form and there is marked difference in ion exchange capacities due to the difference in hydration of the ions.

The ion exchange equilibrium experiments at 30, 50 and 70° were performed and the respective isotherms were plotted. Isotherms for Na⁺→H⁺ and K⁺→H⁺ exchange show hysteresis loops but no loop was observed in Mg²⁺→H⁺, Ca²⁺→H⁺, Sr²⁺→H⁺ and Ba²⁺→H⁺ exchange. It is found with the help of these isotherms that niobium arsenate exchanger is suitable for thermodynamic studies only upto 70° because its reversibility performance is good within this range of temperature.

Ion exchange equilibrium results at 30° are given in Tables 2-7. The ion exchange reaction can be represented as

in which R refers to the niobium arsenate matrix. The selectivity coefficient is given by

$$S_H^M = \frac{\bar{X}_M}{(\bar{X}_H)^n} \frac{(X_H)^n}{X_M} \quad \dots (2)$$

where X_M and X_H refer to mole fractions of metals and hydrogen ions in the exchanger phase, X_M and X_H refer to corresponding mole fractions in the solution phase and n represents the valence of the metal ion.

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant of this exchange reaction may be written in terms of the activity coefficients of

$$K_H^M = \frac{(\bar{X}_M)}{(X_M)} \cdot \frac{(X_H)^n}{(\bar{X}_H)^n} \cdot \frac{(\bar{f}_M)}{(\bar{f}_H)} \cdot \frac{(f_H)^n}{(f_M)^n}$$

$$K_H^M = S_H^M \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_M}{(\bar{f}_H)^n} \cdot \frac{(f_H)^n}{(f_M)^n} \quad \dots (3)$$

The ratio of the activity coefficients in the dilute solution $\frac{(\bar{f}_M)}{(\bar{f}_H)^n}$ will be close to unity at constant ionic strength. This ratio in these exchange experiments has been confirmed with Debye-Huckel limiting equation for solution phase activity coefficients i.e.,

$$\log_{10} \bar{f} = -A \cdot Z_+ \cdot Z_- (\mu)^{1/2} \quad \dots (4)$$

where notations have their usual significances. Hence K_H^M is calculated by the formula

$$K_H^M = S_H^M \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_M}{(\bar{f}_H)^n} \quad \dots (5)$$

The solid phase activity coefficients have been calculated by Ekedahl¹⁵ procedure

$$\ln \bar{f}_M = -(1 - \bar{X}_M) \ln S_H^M + \int_{\bar{X}_M}^1 \ln S_H^M d\bar{X}_M \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\ln \bar{f}_H = \bar{X}_M \ln S_H^M - \int_0^{\bar{X}_M} \ln S_H^M d\bar{X}_M \quad \dots (7)$$

In this way selectivity coefficients, solid phase activity coefficients and thermodynamic equilibrium constants have been calculated for all exchange equilibria at 30, 50 and 70°. The results only for the exchange equilibria at 30 ± 2° are given in Tables 2-7. The obtained values for thermodynamic equilibrium constants K_H^M vs temperature are plotted in Fig. 1. K_H^M values increase as the temperature increases.

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of the thermodynamic equilibrium constants.

With the help of K_H^M , free energy changes (ΔG°) for the ion exchange equilibrium have been calculated as

$$\Delta G^\circ = -\frac{R \cdot T}{Z_H \cdot Z_M} \ln K_H^M \quad \dots (8)$$

where R is the gas constant, Z_H and Z_M are the valences of the competing ions and T absolute

TABLE 8—FREE ENERGY, ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY CHANGES IN THE ION EXCHANGE REACTIONS AT 30 ± 2°

Dis- placing ion	Hydrated radius (Å)	ΔG° cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔH° cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔS° cal. deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta \bar{S}_{EX}$ cal. deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
Na ⁺	2.76	-113.1	496	2.01	16.01
K ⁺	2.92	340.3	66.70	-0.90	23.30
Mg ²⁺	7.00	418.70	-388	-2.66	-34.26
Ca ²⁺	6.30	398.10	-385	-2.52	-13.92
Sr ²⁺	—	285.10	-267	-1.56	-8.86
Ba ²⁺	5.90	152.25	-200	-1.16	+ 1.14

temperature. The results are given in Table 8. In alkaline earth metal ions equilibria, the values of ΔG° varies with the size of ingoing cation. It is larger for the ion having greater hydrated radius.

The ΔH° values have been calculated following the method of Larsen¹⁶ by the Fig. 1 in which $\log_{10} K_H^M$ vs $\frac{10^3}{T}$ are plotted. The results obtained

are presented in Table 8. The ΔH° values indicate that alkali metal ion and alkaline earth metal ion exchange takes place with absorption or evolution of heat respectively. The evolution of heat decreases continuously from Mg²⁺ to Ba²⁺ exchange.

The change in entropy values has been calculated by the following expression :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ \quad \dots (9)$$

and the entropy difference between corresponding ionic forms of the exchanger $\Delta \bar{S}_{EX}$ can be given as

$$\Delta S^\circ = \Delta \bar{S}_{EX} - (S_M^0 - S_H^0) \quad \dots (10)$$

where S_M^0 and S_H^0 refer to aqueous ionic entropies¹⁷. The results are shown in Table 8. ΔS° and $\Delta \bar{S}_{EX}$ values for the exchange equilibria increases with the decrease in hydrated radii of the ingoing ion. There is marked difference between $\Delta \bar{S}_{EX}$ values of Mg²⁺ and Ba²⁺. This difference may suggest that separation of these two ions on niobium arsenate column is possible. The decrease in ΔS° values of the system indicates the higher uptake of the ions. A significant negative contribution of ΔS° results from the replacement of a cation of high S° in the external aqueous phase by one of a lower S° in the exchanger phase. The magnitude of the entropy contribution from the water transfer is mainly dependent upon the water structure in the exchanger phase where it is more or less coordinated. The small entropy change may also be due to less volume available for the hydrated ion in the matrix of the exchanger.

ΔS° and ΔS_{EX}^- values of alkaline earth metal ions exchange show the selectivity sequence as $Ba > Sr > Ca > Mg$. ΔS° value for $Na^+ \rightarrow H^+$ exchange suggests its higher preference by the material. It might therefore be possible to get it separated from the rest of the ions studied.

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